

Review of Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs) related to the Correlation of Phase Equilibrium Data

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<http://hdl.handle.net/10045/122857>

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In this revision, it is possible to find different examples of publicly available MatLab Graphical User Interfaces (GUI's) developed to help researchers and students that have to deal with the challenging problem phase equilibrium data correlation (e.g. LLE, LVE). These examples are:

- GMcal_TieLinesLL: <http://hdl.handle.net/10045/51725>
- GMcal_TieLinesVL: <http://hdl.handle.net/10045/122857>
- Boundaries_LL_NRTL: <http://hdl.handle.net/10045/121471>
- ParamIni_LL_NRTL: <http://hdl.handle.net/10045/130017>

GMcal_TieLinesLL

Graphical User Interface (GUI) for the Topological Analysis of Calculated GM(L) Surfaces and Curves, including Tie-Lines, Hessian Matrix, Spinodal Curve, Critical Point Location, etc. for Binary and Ternary Liquid-Liquid Equilibrium (LLE) Data.
<http://hdl.handle.net/10045/51725>.

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This is a single and very easy-to-use Graphical User Interface (GMcal_TieLinesLL) based on the topological information contained in the Gibbs energy of mixing function. It has been developed for

binary and ternary LLE systems, as a friendly tool to check the coherence of the parameters obtained in a correlation data procedure (the NRTL and UNIQUAC models are included by defect, however any other $G^{\text{Excess}}(\text{L})/\text{RT}$ model could be easily implemented). This analysis of the $G^{\text{M}}(\text{L})/\text{RT}$ surface in the whole range of composition, the $G^{\text{M}}(\text{L})/\text{RT}$ for the binary subsystems and the $G^{\text{M}}(\text{L})/\text{RT}$ curves in planes containing the liquid-liquid tie lines should be necessary to validate the obtained parameters for the different models for correlating phase equilibrium data. This simple analysis could be used by authors and journals in order to guarantee the adequate prediction of equilibrium.

After version 2.2, this GUI also allows, on the one hand, the analysis of the Hessian Matrix determinant (σ), the spinodal curve ($\sigma=0$), and the Plait Point location for LLE ternary systems. On the other hand, it is also possible to analyze binary LLE data at different temperatures, including the location, if there exists, of the Critical Solution Temperature (UCST, LCST or Closed Miscibility Loops), using the NRTL, the UNIQUAC or “other” model. Additionally, the representation of the correlated miscibility boundaries (LLE or mLLE) for the NRTL model depending on the α_{ij} value has been included.

Related papers:

- ✓ Should we trust all the published LLE correlation parameters in phase equilibria? Necessity of their Assessment Prior to Publication. Fluid Phase Equilibria. 2017, 433, 243-252. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.fluid.2016.11.009>.
- ✓ GE Models and Algorithms for Condensed Phase Equilibrium Data Regression in Ternary Systems: Limitations and Proposals. The Open Thermodynamics Journal. 2011, 5, (Suppl 1-M5) 48-62. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2174/1874396X01105010048>.
- ✓ LLE data correlation using NRTL model for different types of binary systems: UCST, LCST and closed miscibility loops. Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research. 2020, 59(17), 8469-8479. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.0c00141>.
- ✓ Checking Liquid-Liquid Critical Plait Conditions and their Application in Ternary Systems. Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research. 2012, 51(13), 5098-5102. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/ie202793r>.

GMcal_TieLinesVL

Graphical User Interface (GUI) for the Topological Analysis of Experimental and Calculated GM Functions for Binary and Ternary (Isobaric or Isothermal) Vapor-Liquid Equilibrium (VLE or VLLE) Data (including Tie-Lines, Derivatives, Distillation Boundaries, LL Critical Points Location, etc.). <http://hdl.handle.net/10045/122857>.

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This GUI, GMcal_TieLinesVL, allows the analysis of experimental and calculated (isobaric or isothermal) vapor-liquid (or vapor-liquid-liquid) equilibrium data for binary and ternary systems, to detect the necessity of considering larger dependences (of temperature or pressure, respectively) in the binary interaction parameters of the model used (e.g. NRTL model) and also to check the consistency of VLE data correlation results through the topological information contained in the Gibbs energy of mixing function.

The new version of the GMcal_TieLinesVL is also useful to analyze the predictions of the model used (when only the parameters of the corresponding models are known) regarding the possibilities of LLE, analyzing possible critical solution points, in the case of binary systems or the Hessian Matrix, Spinodal Curve and possible Plait Point Location in ternary systems in the corresponding range of experimental (isobaric or isothermal) data, and/or to the existence of distillation boundaries.

Related papers:

- ✓ Procedure for the correlation of normal appearance VLE data, where the classical models dramatically fail with no apparent reason. Fluid Phase Equilibria. 2019, 493, 88-101. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fluid.2019.04.001>.
- ✓ The unavoidable necessity of considering temperature dependence of the liquid Gibbs energy of mixing for certain VLE data correlations. Fluid Phase Equilibria. 2018, 473, 17-31. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fluid.2018.05.025>.

Boundaries_LL_NRTL

Graphical User Interface (GUI) for the Characterization of the NRTL Model: Binary Spinodal Surfaces (in the $\tau_{i,j}$ - $\tau_{j,i}$ - x_i space), LLE Maps, and Miscibility Boundaries.
<http://hdl.handle.net/10045/121471>.

This Graphical User Interface (Boundaries_LL_NRTL) has been developed as a friendly tool for the analysis of the NRTL model. This GUI allows the direct visualization and calculation of 3D representations (in the $\tau_{i,j}$ - $\tau_{j,i}$ - x_i space) and 2D projections (in the $\tau_{i,j}$ - $\tau_{j,i}$ plane) of binary spinodal surfaces, LLE maps, and miscibility boundaries of the NRTL model for different values of the non-randomness parameter ($\tau_{i,j}$) between 0 and 0.95.

Related paper:

- ✓ What does the NRTL model look like? Determination of boundaries for different fluid phase equilibrium regions. *AIChE Journal*. 2022, e17805. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/aic.17805>.

ParamIni_LL_NRTL

Graphical User Interface (GUI) for the Selection of NRTL Initial Parameters for the Correlation of Ternary Liquid-Liquid Equilibrium Data (Type I, II, III and 0 (LL island), i.e. with 1, 2, 3 or 0 binary pairs partially miscible). <http://hdl.handle.net/10045/130017>.

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This GUI that allows loading a set of liquid-liquid experimental data to obtain a consistent set of initial NRTL parameters that predicts a parametrized LLE near the experimental one. This set of parameters can be used now in any correlation data algorithm (using the corresponding equilibrium condition: isoactivity, minimum of the global Gibbs energy of mixing, or the Gibbs energy of mixing minor common tangent (plane)) to obtain the final rigorous solution.

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